

Supplemental Materials

Supplementary material includes –

Number of pages: 1-22

Number of tables: 1

Number of figures: 5

Shapiro-Wilk normality test

For *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

W = 0.83571, p-value = 0.09059

For Imipenem-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

W = 0.87847, p-value = 0.09949

For Meropenem-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

W = 0.90917, p-value = 0.4626

Table ST1. Quality assessment of included studies using Newcastle-Ottawa Scale adapted for cross-sectional studies.

Study ID	Methodological quality (max 5 stars)	Comparability (max 2 stars)	Outcome measures and analysis (max 3 stars)	Total score
Shrestha et al., 2015	****	-	**	6
Gupta and Shrestha 2019	***	-	**	5
Shrestha et al., 2019	***	-	**	5
Metok et al., 2020	***	-	**	5
Sherchan and Humagain 2020	****	-	***	7
Yadav et al., 2021	****	-	**	6
Hamal et al., 2021	****	-	***	7

Takahashi et al., 2021	***	-	**	5
Darnal et al., 2021	****	-	**	6
Bhandari et al., 2022	****	-	***	7
Sharma et al., 2023	****	-	***	7

S1 Text

Newcastle-Ottawa Scale adapted for cross-sectional studies

Selection: (Maximum 5 stars)

1) Representativeness of the sample:

- a) **Truly representative of the average in the target population. * (all subjects or random sampling)**
- b) Somewhat representative of the average in the target population. * (non-random sampling)
- c) Selected group of users.
- d) No description of the sampling strategy.

2) Sample size:

- a) **Justified and satisfactory. ***
- b) Not justified.

3) Non-respondents:

- a) Comparability between respondents and non-respondents characteristics is established, and the response rate is satisfactory. *
- b) The response rate is unsatisfactory, or the comparability between respondents and non-respondents is unsatisfactory.
- c) No description of the response rate or the characteristics of the responders and the non-responders.

4) Ascertainment of the exposure (risk factor):

a) **Validated measurement tool.** **

b) Non-validated measurement tool, but the tool is available or described.*

c) No description of the measurement tool.

Comparability: (Maximum 2 stars)

1) The subjects in different outcome groups are comparable, based on the study design or analysis. Confounding factors are controlled.

a) The study controls for the most important factor (select one). *

b) The study control for any additional factor. *

Outcome: (Maximum 3 stars)

1) Assessment of the outcome:

a) **Independent blind assessment.** **

b) Record linkage. **

c) Self report. *

d) No description.

2) Statistical test:

a) **The statistical test used to analyze the data is clearly described and appropriate, and the measurement of the association is presented, including confidence intervals and the probability level (p value).** *

b) The statistical test is not appropriate, not described or incomplete.

This scale has been modified from the Newcastle-Ottawa Quality Assessment Scale for cohort studies to conduct a quality assessment of cross-sectional studies for the meta-analysis, “Carbapenem-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in Nepal: a systematic review and meta-analysis”.

Table ST2. Egger's test for assessment of publication bias for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Egger's regression intercept (Line regression test of funnel plot asymmetry)	
Bias	-3.6237
SE. bias	5.4922
Intercept	-3.623725
SE. intercept	0.7743379
<i>p</i> - value	=0.5386
t	-0.66
Df	5
Multiplicative residual heterogeneity variance (tau ²)	5.422751
Predictor	Standard Error
Weight	Inverse Variance
Reference	Egger et al. (1997)

Table ST3. Egger's test for assessment of publication bias for Imipenem-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Egger's regression intercept (Line regression test of funnel plot asymmetry)	
Bias	-1.2346
SE. bias	3.0053
Intercept	-1.2345
SE. intercept	0.9407
<i>p</i> - value	=0.6908
t	-0.41
Df	9
Multiplicative residual heterogeneity variance (tau ²)	3.0058
Predictor	Standard Error
Weight	Inverse Variance

Reference	Egger et al. (1997)
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Table ST4. Egger's test for assessment of publication bias for Meropenem-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Egger's regression intercept (Line regression test of funnel plot asymmetry)	
Bias	-4.7646
SE. bias	4.6892
Intercept	-4.764634
SE. intercept	1.627238
<i>p</i> - value	0.3844
t	-1.02
Df	3
Multiplicative residual heterogeneity variance (tau ²)	1.628134
Predictor	Standard Error
Weight	Inverse Variance
Reference	Egger et al. (1997)